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RESEARCH ON THE CAUSES OF DEATH OF HONEY BEE
COLONIES *APIS MELLIFERA* L. INHABITING LOG HIVES
IN THE KŁODZKA VALLEY – CASE STUDY

*Ricerca sulle cause di morte delle colonie di api da miele Apis mellifera L.
viventi in alveari all'interno di tronchi nella Valle di Klodzka - un caso studio*

Tree beekeeping in Poland has at least 1000 years of history, proven by carbon dating of the oldest found tree hive (PASTWINSKI, 1985). Although tree beekeeping has disappeared for a while after world war II, now it is getting more and more popular. On December 17, 2020, Tree beekeeping culture was entered on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, upon the proposal of Poland and Belarus. Also, many new projects of return of the honey bee to the forest are being realized, and thousands of log hives produced and hung on trees. Usual log hive has capacity of 40-100 liters, small entrance about 10-20 square centimeters placed over 4 meters above the ground level. Moreover, spacing of log hives in forests is at least several tens of meters, often reaching over 1 kilometer, which should make a difference in horizontal pathogen transfer (SEELEY & SMITH, 2015). The environment of the log hive simulates, rather well, what is described as natural habitat of the honey bee colony (SEELEY & MORSE, 1976) and fits its preferences (SEELEY & MORSE, 1978). Taking those facts into consideration, it is curious what are the reasons of death of such colonies and what are the levels of pathogen infestations in those cases.

To find out, in the beginning of May 2021, we have inspected and collected samples (consisting of dead bees and organic material from the bottom of the nest, combs with brood, dead bees, empty or filled with honey) from 16 dead colonies. All of which, were spaced in the two

agglomerations in forests of Poland at Kłodzka Valley in log hives. Based on macroscopic evaluation and flotation of dead bees, we have estimated levels of infestation with *Varroa destructor* mites. We have taken under consideration: the number of mites separated and attached to bees, DWV symptoms and deformed or unusually small bees. Mites were found in 13 samples (81.25%), from which 6 (37.5%) were classified as highly infested. The degree of bee malnutrition and the possibility of hunger occurring in those colonies were also assessed macroscopically. This assessment was carried out partially in the field. Factors indicating the occurrence of hunger were present in 14 colonies (87.5%). What is worth mentioning only 3 (18.75%) nests appeared to be older than 1 year. Samples were also microscopically examined for the presence and abundance of *Nosema* spp. spores (TOPOLSKA & HARTWIG, 2005), to determine the development of nosemosis. Spores of *Nosema* spp. were detected in 13 samples (81.25%). In 7 cases (43.75%) high infection levels were determined. The presence of viruses - SBV, ABPV, CBPV, BQCV, was also checked using the AGID method. The study showed no viruses present in samples. But DWV symptoms were found in 3 colonies. Stonebrood (*Aspergillus flavus* L.) was detected in one sample. The assessment of the degree of *Varroa destructor* development in 5 samples (37.5%) was probably not reliable, in terms of their quantity or quality. In case of these 5 colonies, mite levels were most likely higher than indicated in performed tests. The absence of viruses in the samples was also clouded by poor sample quality, which, among other things, includes remaining of dead bees in the log hives for too long after death.

The result shows that all colonies were suffering from diseases and in most cases (>75%) they were significant contributing factor or the main cause of death. Unsurprisingly as much as 87.5% of colonies died of starvation. 81.25% of described nests belonged to founder colonies. Our results are similar with those of SEELEY (2017), who found that there was only 23% chance for founder colonies of wild bees in Arnot forest to survive winter. Even though, the colonies were widely spread in the forest, the pathogen infestation levels were very high in many cases. It might be due to a large number of apiaries in Kłodzka Valley, which boosted horizontal transfer of pathogens to the level, in which spacing does not make any difference. Especially when the food sources are scarce (probable reason of common hunger), which leads to more bees using the same forage and robbing behaviors (PECK *et al.*, 2016) are also more likely to occur. Further research, also on surviving colonies and the evaluation of the origins of bees (subspecies), should be carried out in the future.

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